

Phenoxy Acetyl Acetophenone as an Analytical Reagent for Iron

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A new spectrophotometric method for the microdetermination of iron using phenoxy acetyl acetophenone is described. The complex is formed instantaneously, in cold and at pH 5.5. It can be extracted in toluene and shows maximum absorbance at 390 nm. Beer's law is valid over the range of 0.5–8.0 $\mu\text{g Fe/ml}$. The complex is stable and sensitivity of determination is 0.0081 $\mu\text{g Fe/cm}^2$. Many common ions are tolerated to a large extent. The method is simple and can be used satisfactorily for the determination of iron in drugs and ores.

SEVERAL reagents have been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of iron^{1,2}. The metal is known to be present in small amounts in various synthetic and natural objects and investigations are now mainly centred in suggesting new methods for estimation of iron in trace quantity in such objects. Some very sensitive reagents are recently reported for its estimation in ores, alloys, water, drugs and biological materials³⁻⁹.

In the present studies, a new diketone compound, phenoxy acetyl acetophenone (PAA), has been investigated as an analytical reagent for trace determination of iron in drugs and ores. The reagent was synthesized and used. It forms a yellowish red complex with Fe(II) as well as Fe(III). The complex is extractable in toluene and shows maximum absorbance at 390 nm. The colour development is instantaneous and there is negligible interference from other transition metals commonly associated with iron. The reagent is sensitive and can be used to determine iron in drugs and ores.

Experimental

Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with quartz cuvettes of 1 cm thickness was used for spectrophotometric measurements.

Iron(II) solution (0.05 M) was prepared by dissolving a known weight of ferrous ammonium sulphate (A. R.) in distilled water and was standardized¹⁰. Solutions used in the studies contained 25 $\mu\text{g Fe/ml}$. Fresh solutions were always used.

Acetate buffer, pH 5.5 was prepared by taking appropriate quantities of 1 M solutions of sodium acetate and acetic acid.

The reagent PAA was synthesized from phenoxy acetic acid. This acid itself was prepared by the reaction of phenol and chloroacetic acid in NaOH¹¹. The ethyl ester of phenoxy acetic acid, when treated with acetophenone in presence of potassium *tert*-butoxide underwent Stobbe condensation to yield pinkish white phenoxy acetyl acetophenone¹². It

was crystallized from ethyl alcohol. (Found : C, 75.45 ; H, 5.58. Calcd. C, 75.59 ; H, 5.51% ; m.p. 80°). 5 ml of 1.77×10^{-3} M solution of PAA in acetone was used in the studies.

Ore samples were obtained from Indian Bureau of Mines, Nagpur.

General procedure : An aliquot of solution containing 5 to 80 μg of iron was taken in a beaker. 10 ml of acetate buffer of pH 5.5 was added and the total volume was made upto 20 ml with distilled water. To it was added 5 ml of 1.77×10^{-3} M solution of PAA in acetone. The yellowish orange Fe-PAA complex formed instantaneously. The solution was transferred to a separatory funnel and equilibrated for 30 sec with 10 ml toluene. The organic layer was separated and its absorbance was read at 390 nm against a reagent blank prepared in an identical manner. The concentration of iron in an unknown solution was calculated with the help of a calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Optimum conditions : The complexation reaction is instantaneous and takes place in cold. One extraction with 10 ml of toluene and shaking period of 30 sec is sufficient for quantitative extraction of iron. The complex is highly stable ; the absorbance remains constant for 8 days. The extraction behaviour of Fe-PAA complex as a function of pH was studied. It is found that extraction is quantitative between pH 5.0-6.0. Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer is most suitable to maintain the pH and 10 ml of acetate buffer of pH 5.5 was used in the studies. The result remains unaffected even if the volume of buffer is varied from 5 to 15 ml. Potassium hydrogen phthalate-NaOH and sodium hydrogen phosphate-potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffers are also suitable for quantitative extraction while with sodium citrate-NaOH buffer of pH 5.5 extraction is found to be 36% only. 5 ml of 1.77×10^{-3} M PAA solution in acetone (metal

reagent ratio 1 : 20) is necessary for complete complexation. Excess of reagent does not make any difference in the absorbance. Toluene and ethyl acetate quantitatively extract the iron-complex while other solvents such as chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, *n*-hexanol, *n*-butanol and *n*-amyl alcohol give a lower absorbance.

Spectral characteristics : The spectra of Fe-PAA complex against reagent blank is shown in Fig. 1. It shows two maxima ; one at 390 nm and another at 450 nm. The λ_{max} at 390 nm is more prominent and hence all the measurements were made at 390 nm. Under the conditions, the reagent alone does not show any absorbance against the solvent blank. Both Fe(II) and Fe(III) react identically with the reagent. The range in which Beer's law is followed is found to be from 0.5-8.0 $\mu\text{g Fe/ml}$. The optimum range of iron determination as evaluated from Ringbom plot is 1.0-7.9 $\mu\text{g Fe/ml}$. Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity are 0.0081 $\mu\text{g Fe/cm}^2$ and $6.813 \times 10^4 \text{ l.mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. From 10 different sets of observations, the relative standard deviation was found to be 1.6%.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra. Fe=25 μg , pH=5.5, 5 ml of $1.77 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M PAA}$

Effect of diverse ions : Several foreign ions were examined for their effect on the extraction behaviour of iron. The tolerance limit was calculated as that amount of foreign ion required to cause a $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of iron. The results are given in Table 1. EDTA interferes strongly in the determination and must not be present. Many transition metals generally associated with iron in alloys, ores etc. were found to be tolerated upto very high concentration.

Determination of iron in drugs : Iron present in drugs in the form of ferrous sulphate, ferrous succinate and ferrous fumarate can be conveniently determined by this method. For this, tablets or capsules containing iron in the form of ferrous sulphate or ferrous succinate were placed in a beaker. To it was added 50 ml of distilled water containing 2 to 3 ml of conc. HCl and the mixture was boiled

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS
Fe=25 μg , pH=5.5, $\lambda=390 \text{ nm}$

Ion present	Tolerance limit (μg)	Ion present	Tolerance limit (μg)
Cl ⁻	17700	Ag ⁺	4300
I ⁻	5050	Mg ²⁺	1900
SCN ⁻	2300	Mn ²⁺	2200
SO ₄ ²⁻	5800	Co ²⁺	3550
S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	6700	Ni ²⁺	2600
Cr ₂ O ₇ ²⁻	21600	Cu ²⁺	2550
oxalate	3500	Zn ²⁺	2600
citrate	5600	Hg ²⁺	6000
tartrate	5900	Pb ²⁺	8300
EDTA	None	Al ³⁺	54

until complete dissolution occurred. The boiling mixture was filtered through a filter paper previously rinsed with distilled water. The residue was washed with 20 ml of boiling distilled water and the final volume of filtrate was made upto 250 ml in a volumetric flask with distilled water. In case of tablet or capsule containing iron as ferrous fumarate, digestion with 20 ml of conc. H₂SO₄ for 2-3 hr in a Kjeldahl flask was carried out. The solution was transferred to a beaker, concentrated to about 1 ml, cooled and diluted with distilled water. Insoluble matter was removed by filtration and the filtrate was made upto 250 ml in a volumetric flask with distilled water. In case of liquid samples, 2 ml of the liquid was diluted with distilled water in a 250 ml volumetric flask containing 2 ml of conc. HCl. In all cases, solution containing nearly 25 μg of iron per ml was prepared by suitable dilution and the procedure was followed. 10 tablets/capsules or liquid portions were taken in each case and experiments were performed 4 times. In every case, the result obtained was compared with the standard O-phenanthroline method for iron estimation^{1,2}. The results obtained are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF IRON IN DRUGS

Name of the drug	Manufacturer	Iron present as	Iron* present (mg)	Iron found (mg)	% Error
Iberol	Abbott Laboratories	Ferrous sulphate	105.00	106.00	0.95
Tablets of FeSO ₄ and Folic Acid Folate	Eupharma Laboratories	Ferrous sulphate	12.08	11.95	1.07
Geriatone	Alembic Chemicals	Ferrous fumarate	82.13	82.13	0.00
Hematrine	Alembic Chemicals	Ferrous sulphate	12.08	12.26	1.49
Becadexamine	Sandoz Pharmaceuticals	Ferrous succinate	32.94	31.93	3.00
Compoferon	Glaxo Laboratories	Ferrous fumarate	16.42	16.25	1.08
Fesofar	Bayer India Ltd.	Ferrous sulphate	60.28	59.45	1.37
Siderfol	Reptakos Brett and Co.	Ferrous sulphate	30.21	30.12	0.29
Iberol	Smith, Kline and French Co.	Ferrous fumarate	98.92	97.9	0.93
	Abbott Laboratories	Ferrous sulphate	26.25	26.25	0.00

* O-phenanthroline method.

Determination of iron in ores :

Procedure : About 0.4 g of sample (120 mesh) was weighed accurately and dissolved in a mixture of conc. HCl and HNO₃ (15+10 ml). The solution was heated till all the nitrous fumes were removed. 20 ml of 1 : 1 H₂SO₄ was added and the solution was evaporated almost to dryness. 50 ml of distilled water was added and the residue was digested till all the salts dissolved. It was cooled and filtered through a filter paper previously rinsed with distilled water. The working solution (nearly 25 µg Fe/ml) was prepared by appropriate dilution of this solution. 1 ml of this solution was taken and the procedure was followed. The experiments were performed with 10 different portions of solutions and the results were compared with standard O-phenanthroline method^{1,2}. The results obtained are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF IRON IN ORES

Ore	Iron present* %	Iron found %	% Error
Sample 1	50.26	50.59	0.33
Sample 2	39.41	39.50	0.09

* O-phenanthroline method.

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